

Statistical Tolerance Intervals for Randomized Response Designs

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Abstract

Randomized response techniques (RRTs) provide a reliable framework for eliciting truthful answers to sensitive questions while protecting respondents' privacy. Building on the seminal work of Warner, ["Randomized Response: A Survey Technique for Eliminating Evasive Answer Bias", *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 60(309):63–69, 1965] and subsequent improvements, this paper advances the statistical toolkit for RRTs by developing tolerance intervals as an informative metric. Tolerance intervals guarantee, with a specified confidence level, that a predetermined proportion of the sampled population falls within the calculated interval. In contrast to confidence intervals, tolerance intervals often serve as a diagnostic tool for outlier detection or to provide limits to understand where a set proportion of the sampled population lies, which in turn can be used to identify possible changes to the underlying sampled population's distribution over time. Such topics are of potential interest to survey statisticians, however, the use of tolerance intervals for these purposes have been scantily employed in the analysis of survey data. We proceed to demonstrate the utility of tolerance intervals for the latter of these objectives in the context of RRTs. We examine classical RRT models alongside universal methods proposed in the more recent literature. We investigate empirical coverage probabilities under various settings through extensive simulation studies, which address the effect of sample sizes, random response probabilities, and coverage levels. An example of a cheating study illustrates the practical advantages and trade-offs among the methods. Our findings provide comprehensive guidance on selecting appropriate tolerance in-

terval construction for sensitive survey data and highlight avenues for future research.

Keywords: Binomial distribution, confidence intervals, coverage study, privacy protection, survey data, Warner's model.

1 Introduction

Surveys on sensitive topics, such as abortion, political affiliation, criminal behavior, or other polarizing issues, pose a significant challenge to researchers: *How can one elicit truthful responses while safeguarding respondent confidentiality?* Randomized response techniques (RRTs) provide a rigorous solution by employing randomization devices that allow indirect answering of sensitive questions. Over the years, RRTs have evolved to encompass both categorical and quantitative data, broadening their applicability to a diverse array of research domains where anonymity is crucial.

A central challenge in survey sampling, particularly when addressing sensitive issues, is quantifying an estimate's inherent uncertainty and variability. Indeed, the precision of such an estimate affects the accuracy of subsequent summaries and inferential results, such as those characterized by statistical intervals. The two most commonly employed statistical intervals are confidence intervals, which provide bounds with a specified degree of confidence for a population parameter of interest, and prediction intervals, which provide bounds with a specified degree of confidence for one or more future observations drawn from the underlying population. Tolerance intervals, however, provide bounds for a specified proportion of the sampled population with a given confidence level. In the context of survey data, tolerance intervals have the potential function as a diagnostic tool to detect shifts or outliers in the collected data, revealing changes from one survey to the next, over successive years, or across different regions. This capability is particularly valuable for monitoring the evolution of public opinion on contentious issues over time or

in various contexts.

The pioneering work of Warner (1965) laid the foundation for RRTs by introducing a probabilistic method to mitigate evasive responses. In the Warner technique approach, each respondent uses a randomization device to decide whether to provide a direct or complementary answer, thus increasing the confidentiality of the respondents. This innovative framework not only reduced response bias, but also spurred a series of methodological refinements that have significantly advanced the field of survey sampling.

Building on the Warner technique, subsequent innovations – including the unrelated question model by Greenberg et al. (1969) – have progressively improved estimation techniques and enhanced privacy protections. Early developments introduced multiplicative noise (Eichhorn and Hayre, 1983) and optional response techniques (Chaudhuri and Mukerjee, 1985), while later work by Fox and Tracy (1984), Bhargava and Singh (2000), and Gupta et al. (2002) explored additive scrambling and modified randomization devices. Subsequent refinements combined additive and multiplicative methods (Gjestvang and Singh, 2009; Diana and Perri, 2011) and incorporated Bayesian approaches for enhanced analysis (Al-Sobhi et al., 2016; Chung et al., 2018). More recent contributions (cf. Gupta et al., 2018, 2022; Khalil et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2021; Saleem and Sanaullah, 2022; Zapata et al., 2023; Azeem, 2023) have advanced efficiency, privacy metrics, and novel estimators. Despite these advances, the explicit construction of tolerance intervals in RRT remains unexplored.

Although we do not provide an exhaustive review of all available RRTs, our contributions are fourfold. First, we review methods that closely resem-

ble Warner’s original technique, such as [Devore \(1977\)](#) and [Singh and Joarder \(1997\)](#), Greenberg’s unrelated question model, such as (cf. [Greenberg et al., 1969](#); [Soberanis-Cruz et al., 2008](#); [Mangat et al., 1992](#)), in that we focus on binary outcome RRTs under simple random sampling with replacement (SR-SWR) in scenarios with unknown population sizes and focus on their interval construction strategies. Second, we examine other prominent approaches to construct confidence intervals in RRTs, including those developed by [Chang and Kuo \(2012\)](#), [Frey and Pérez \(2012\)](#), and [Shan \(2016\)](#). Third, we extend these methodologies by constructing tolerance intervals tailored to the reviewed RRTs. Fourth, our comprehensive routines contribute to the R package `tolerance` [Young \(2010\)](#) by incorporating new functionalities into the subfunction `bintol.int` with a new `RR` option to facilitate the estimation of tolerance intervals specifically designed for randomized responses. For further background on RRTs, readers are encouraged to consult the `RRTCS` package [Del Mar Rueda et al. \(2016\)](#) and the work of [Chaudhuri \(2011\)](#) for detailed expositions on randomized response strategies. We refer to the text by [Krishnamoorthy and Mathew \(2009\)](#) for an expansive treatment of the theoretical foundations and applications of tolerance intervals.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the selected RRTs and discuss the corresponding constructions of confidence intervals. Section 3 examines the development of tolerance intervals for randomized responses by adapting the method of [Hahn and Chandra \(1981\)](#). Section 4 presents a numerical study to evaluate the performance and coverage of the proposed methods. Section 5 illustrates practical applications of

Table 1.1: Summary of Symbols and Their Definitions

Symbol	Description
π	True proportion of individuals with the sensitive attribute.
$\hat{\pi}$	Estimator of the sensitive proportion.
$\hat{\pi}_{\text{Yes}}$	Observed proportion of “Yes” responses in randomized response surveys.
p	Probability of drawing a sensitive card (in Warner’s method).
$1 - p$	Proportion of non-sensitive cards (in Warner’s method.)
$z_{\alpha/2}$	Critical value from the standard normal distribution for a confidence level of $1 - \alpha$.
α	Significance level of the confidence.
π_U	The probability of answering ‘yes’ for the unrelated question (assumed known for this paper).
π	Parameter of interest (e.g., a population parameter used in tolerance interval construction).
$\hat{\pi}$	Sample estimate of the parameter π .
L	Lower bound of a tolerance interval.
U	Upper bound of a tolerance interval.
P	Content level, i.e., desired proportion of the population to be captured by the tolerance interval.
n	Sample size.
m	Future sample size used for constructing tolerance intervals.
π_L, π_U	Lower and upper bounds of the confidence interval for π for RRT.
N_L, N_U	Lower and upper count thresholds for constructing binomial tolerance intervals.
\mathbf{X}	Random Sample representing the observed data or responses.
x	Observed data or responses
$F(x \pi, n)$	Cumulative distribution function (CDF) of \mathbf{X} given parameter π and sample size n .
$I\{\cdot\}$	Indicator function, equal to 1 if the specified condition is true and 0 otherwise.
$\chi_{\alpha,1}^2$	Critical value from the chi-squared distribution with 1 degree of freedom at significance level α .
$\text{LR}(\pi_{\text{Yes}}, x, n)$	Likelihood ratio for estimating π_{Yes} given observed data x and sample size n .

these techniques. Finally, Section 6 concludes with a synthesis of our findings, highlighting their practical implications and suggesting directions for future research. Since this paper employs an extensive array of symbols and notation, we provide a comprehensive Table 1.1 that lists each symbol along with its definition.

2 Confidence Intervals Used for RRT Models

Tolerance intervals for discrete distributions typically inherit similar coverage properties as confidence intervals used for the underlying location parameter of that discrete distribution. Thus, it is important to have accurate confidence interval construction under RRTs. In this section, we review methods

tailored for binary outcomes generated by various RRT models. We begin by discussing six specific techniques: Warner’s original model (Warner, 1965), along with variants introduced by Devore (1977), Singh and Joarder (1997), Greenberg et al. (1969), Soberanis-Cruz et al. (2008), and Mangat et al. (1992). Each model provides a distinct estimation mechanism for the sensitive proportion π , involving a unique combination of randomization schemes and auxiliary information. Thus, each of these RRT models use a different maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) and variance formula, whereas the construction of confidence intervals follows a common form. Specifically, for each model, a confidence interval for π is constructed using the normal approximation

$$\hat{\pi} \pm z_{\alpha/2} \sqrt{\hat{V}_M(\hat{\pi})},$$

where $\hat{V}_M(\hat{\pi})$ denotes the model-specific variance and $z_{\alpha/2}$ is the critical value from the standard normal distribution corresponding to the desired confidence level $1 - \alpha$. The specific expressions for $\hat{\pi}$ and $\hat{V}_M(\hat{\pi})$ for each of the six RRTs we study are summarized in Table 2.1. In Section 2.1, we describe the response mechanisms and rationales behind each RRT model. The detailed mathematical formulations are omitted for brevity and are instead consolidated in the referenced table.

Finally, we review three universal methods for constructing confidence or tolerance intervals that are agnostic to the specific RRT model. These include approaches developed by Frey and Pérez (2012), Chang and Kuo (2012), and Shan (2016), which offer generalized inferential procedures applicable across

a broad class of randomized response data structures. These are presented in Section 2.2.

2.1 Warner-Type Methods

Table 2.1: Maximum Likelihood Estimators and Variances for RRTs

Method (M)	Estimator $\hat{\pi}$	Variance $\hat{V}_M(\hat{\pi})$
Warner (W)	$\frac{\hat{\pi}_{\text{Yes}} - (1-p)}{2p-1}$	$\frac{\hat{\pi}(1-\hat{\pi})}{n-1} + \frac{p(1-p)}{(n-1)(2p-1)^2}$
Devore (D)	$\frac{\hat{\pi}_{\text{Yes}} - (1-p)}{p}$	$\frac{\hat{\pi}(1-\hat{\pi})}{2(n-1)} + \frac{p(1-p)}{2(n-1)(2p-1)^2}$
Horvitz (H)	$\frac{\hat{\pi}_{\text{Yes}} - (1-p)\pi_U}{p}$	$\frac{\hat{\pi}(1-\hat{\pi})}{2(n-1)} + \frac{p(1-p)}{2(n-1)(2p-1)^2}$
Soberanis-Cruz (SC)	$\frac{\hat{\pi}_{\text{Yes}} - \pi_U(1-p)}{p}$	$\frac{\hat{\pi}(1-\hat{\pi})}{n-1} + \frac{1}{n-1} \left(\frac{(1-p)p}{p^2} + \frac{(p-1)}{p} \hat{\pi} \right)$
Mangat-Singh-Singh (MSS)	$\frac{\hat{\pi}_{\text{Yes}} - (1-p)\pi_U}{1 - (1-p)\pi_U}$	$\frac{\hat{\pi}(1-\hat{\pi})}{(n-1)[1 - \pi_U(1-p)]^2}$
Singh-Joarder (SJ)	$\frac{\hat{\pi}_{\text{Yes}} - (1-p)}{(2p-1) + p(1-p)}$	$\frac{\hat{\pi}(1-\hat{\pi})}{(n-1)[2p-1 + p(1-p)]^2}$

2.1.1 Warner's Model

The Warner model ([Warner, 1965](#)) is a foundational RRT designed to protect respondent privacy while estimating the proportion of a sensitive attribute in a population. In this method, each respondent draws a card from a box containing a proportion p of cards marked with the sensitive trait A , and the remaining proportion $1 - p$ marked with A^c . The respondent then provides a “yes” response if the card drawn matches their actual status and a “no” otherwise. The observed proportion of “yes” responses, $\hat{\pi}_{\text{Yes}}$, is used to infer the true proportion of individuals with the sensitive trait. The Warner model has been widely studied and forms the basis for many subsequent developments in RRTs, serving as a benchmark for evaluating alternative methods.

2.1.2 Horvitz’s Model

The Horvitz model ([Greenberg et al., 1969](#)) is an extension of Warner’s RRT that incorporates an unrelated innocuous question to improve respondent privacy and cooperation. In this model, each respondent randomly selects one of two questions: a sensitive question related to the attribute of interest or an innocuous question with a known proportion π_U of individuals possessing the innocuous attribute. This approach allows for unbiased estimation of the sensitive attribute while maintaining confidentiality.

In the Horvitz model, a box contains a proportion p of cards marked with the sensitive question and a proportion $1 - p$ marked with the unrelated, innocuous question. The Horvitz model offers an effective alternative to direct questioning by leveraging an unrelated question to further mask respondent identity. The model has been widely applied in surveys dealing with highly-sensitive topics, where privacy concerns might otherwise hinder accurate data collection.

2.1.3 Devore’s Model

The Devore model ([Devore, 1977](#)) is a variant of the RRT that further enhances respondent privacy while maintaining the integrity of population proportion estimation. In this approach, each respondent draws a card from a box containing a proportion p of cards marked with the sensitive trait A , and a proportion $1 - p$ marked with the innocuous trait B . The respondent then reports “yes” if they belong to the sensitive group and draw an A , otherwise, they report “yes” unconditionally.

The observed proportion of “yes” responses, $\hat{\pi}_{\text{Yes}}$, is used to estimate the true proportion of individuals with the sensitive trait. The variance expression in the Devore model is similar to the variance in the Horvitz model, but with the assumption that $\pi_U = 1$. By incorporating an innocuous question element, the Devore model provides greater anonymity and is particularly useful in situations where respondents may hesitate to disclose sensitive information directly.

2.1.4 Soberanis and Cruz’s Model

The Soberanis-Cruz model ([Soberanis-Cruz et al., 2008](#)) builds upon the Horvitz model by incorporating an innocuous variable that is correlated with the sensitive variable of interest. This approach aims to improve the estimation efficiency by leveraging auxiliary information while maintaining respondent privacy. In this model, each respondent randomly selects one of two questions: a sensitive question or an innocuous question correlated with the sensitive attribute. The response follows the mechanism:

$$\pi_{\text{Yes}} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the card corresponds to the sensitive attribute;} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The Soberanis-Cruz model offers an enhancement over traditional RRTs by utilizing auxiliary information to reduce variance and improve the precision of the estimation, making it particularly useful for finite population surveys where additional contextual information is available.

2.1.5 Mangat, Singh, and Singh's Model

The Mangat-Singh-Singh model, introduced in [Mangat \(1994\)](#), is an improved randomized response strategy aimed at enhancing respondent privacy while maintaining statistical efficiency. This model modifies the unrelated question technique by allowing respondents to answer “yes” based on a two-stage randomized process that increases the security of sensitive responses. The procedure for the Mangat-Singh-Singh model involves the following steps:

- If a respondent belongs to the sensitive group A , they answer “yes.”
- If they belong to group A^c (i.e., not having the sensitive attribute), they draw a card from a box containing a proportion p of cards marked A and a proportion $1 - p$ of cards marked B .
- If the card is marked B and they possess the innocuous attribute B (known with proportion π_U), they answer “yes.” Otherwise, they answer “no.”

The variance in the Mangat-Singh-Singh model accounts for the randomness introduced by the two-stage randomization process and the uncertainty due to sampling, and the model improves upon the earlier Warner-type model approaches by increasing respondent privacy and reducing the bias introduced by evasive answer tendencies, making it a robust choice for surveys involving highly-sensitive questions.

2.1.6 Singh and Joarder's Model

The Singh-Joarder model ([Singh and Joarder, 1997](#)) is a modification of Warner's RRT that introduces an additional level of randomization to further protect respondent privacy. This model, also known as the "unknown repeated trials" model, enhances the reliability of responses while maintaining the anonymity of respondents.

In the Singh-Joarder model, respondents in group A^c report membership if directed by a card drawn from a mix of cards marked A and A^c in proportions p and $1 - p$, respectively. If a respondent belongs to group A , they draw a second card if the first card directs them to admit membership, delaying their response. This procedure again is intended to ensure an additional layer of privacy for the respondents.

The response mechanism is defined as follows:

$$\pi_{\text{Yes}} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the respondent answers "yes";} \\ 0, & \text{if the respondent answers "no".} \end{cases}$$

The variance in the Singh-Joarder model accounts for the additional randomization introduced by repeated trials, leading to increased efficiency compared to the Warner model, and the model offers improved efficiency compared to the Warner model, especially when the proportion p is greater than 0.5. Empirical studies have shown that the model achieves greater accuracy in estimating sensitive proportions.

2.2 Universal Methods

2.2.1 Frey and Pérez Exact Confidence Interval

The likelihood-based confidence interval approach developed by [Frey and Pérez \(2012\)](#) provides an exact method for estimating binomial proportions in randomized response surveys. This method relies on the likelihood ratio test to construct confidence intervals that account for the bounded nature of proportions, ensuring valid inference even for small sample sizes or extreme proportions.

Suppose X is the number of “yes” responses received from any RRT in Section 2.1 and x is the observed value. Then, the likelihood ratio two-sided $(1 - \alpha)$ confidence interval for the binomial proportion π_{yes} is obtained by solving the following inequality:

$$-2 \log \text{LR}(\pi_{\text{yes}}, x, n) < \chi_{\alpha,1}^2,$$

where:

- n is the sample size,
- the likelihood ratio test (LRT) statistic is defined as

$$\text{LR}(\pi_{\text{yes}}, x, n) = \frac{\pi_{\text{yes}}^x (1 - \pi_{\text{yes}})^{n-x}}{\hat{\pi}_{\text{yes}}^x (1 - \hat{\pi}_{\text{yes}})^{n-x}},$$

- The MLE of π is $\hat{\pi}_{\text{yes}} = \frac{x}{n}$, and
- $\chi_{\alpha,1}^2$ is the upper α -percentile of the chi-squared distribution with one

degree of freedom.

To improve performance of this approach, particularly with small or extremely sample proportions, [Frey and Pérez \(2012\)](#) introduced adjustments for cases where x is near 0 or n . For values of x such that $\sqrt{n} < x < n - \sqrt{n}$, the confidence interval is defined as the set of all π such that $\text{LR}(\pi_{\text{yes}}, x, n) > c$. For extreme values of $x < \sqrt{n}$ or $x > n - \sqrt{n}$, the interval is expanded using $c/5$ instead of c , thus improving coverage. When the parameter π is bounded within an interval $[a, b] \subset [0, 1]$, the following constrained MLE is used:

$$\hat{\pi}_{\text{yes}} = \text{median} \left\{ a, \frac{x}{n}, b \right\}.$$

Finally, the confidence interval is derived by inverting the LRT, which yields the following:

$$\pi_{\text{yes}} \in \begin{cases} \{ \pi_{\text{yes}} \in [a, b] \mid \text{LR}_{[a,b]}(\pi_{\text{yes}}, x, n) > \frac{c}{5} \}, & \text{for extreme values;} \\ \{ \pi_{\text{yes}} \in [a, b] \mid \text{LR}_{[a,b]}(\pi, x, n) > c \}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The observed proportion of “yes” responses, π_{yes} , and the true proportion π in randomized response models satisfy the linear relationship

$$\pi_{\text{yes}} = v\pi + w,$$

where $v = 1 - p$ and $w = 2p - 1$ in Warner’s model. If $(L(X), U(X))$ is the exact likelihood ratio confidence interval for π_{yes} , the corresponding interval

for π is obtained as follows:

$$(L'(X), U'(X)) = \left(\frac{L(X) - v}{w}, \frac{U(X) - v}{w} \right).$$

2.2.2 Chang and Kuo's Confidence Intervals

Chang and Kuo (2012) developed a set of confidence intervals to estimate the proportion of the population in randomized response surveys by applying Wilson-type confidence interval construction. Their approach provides three confidence intervals that improve the efficiency of estimation while maintaining privacy in sensitive attribute surveys. In their general formulation, Chang and Kuo (2012) and Shan (2016) established a relationship between the observed proportion of “yes” responses π_{yes} and the true proportion of interest π as

$$\pi_{\text{yes}} = v\pi + w.$$

Solving the above to get a formula for $\hat{\pi}$ yields

$$\hat{\pi} = \frac{\hat{\pi}_{\text{yes}} - v}{w},$$

where

- $\hat{\pi}_{\text{yes}}$ is the observed sample proportion in the randomized response survey,
- v and w are model-specific parameters, and
- the values of v and w for different randomized response models as follows:

- Warner’s model: $v = 1 - p$, $w = 2p - 1$,
- Unrelated-question model: $v = (1 - p)\pi_y$, $w = p$,
- Devore’s model: $v = 1 - p$, $w = p$.

The first confidence interval is constructed using the Wilson-type method and is given by:

$$CI_1 = D_1 \pm z_{\alpha/2} \sqrt{V_1},$$

where:

$$D_1 = W_1 \frac{\hat{\pi}_{yes} - v}{w} + (1 - W_1) \frac{1 - 2v}{2w}$$

$$V_1 = \frac{W_1 \hat{\pi}_{yes} (1 - \hat{\pi}_{yes})}{(n + z_{\alpha/2}^2) w^2} + \frac{1 - W_1}{4(n + z_{\alpha/2}^2) w^2}$$

$$W_1 = \frac{n}{n + z_{\alpha/2}^2}.$$

The second confidence interval builds upon the first, but applies a different weighting approach for improved estimation performance:

$$CI_2 = D_2 \pm z_{\alpha/2} \sqrt{V_2},$$

where:

$$D_2 = W_2 \frac{\hat{\pi}_{yes} - v}{w} + (1 - W_2) \frac{1 - 2v}{2w}$$

$$V_2 = \frac{n}{4(n + \sqrt{n})^2 w^2}$$

$$W_2 = \frac{n}{n + \sqrt{n}}.$$

Finally, the third confidence interval incorporates an additional correction term to further refine the estimation accuracy:

$$CI_3 = D_3 \pm z_{\alpha/2} \sqrt{V_3},$$

where:

$$D_3 = W_3 \frac{\hat{\pi}_{yes} - v}{w} + (1 - W_3) \frac{1 - 2v}{2w}$$

$$V_3 = \left(\frac{z_{\alpha/2}^2 - 1}{z_{\alpha/2}^2} \right) \left[\frac{W_3 \hat{\pi}_{yes} (1 - \hat{\pi}_{yes})}{(n + z_{\alpha/2}^2 - 1)w^2} + \frac{1 - W_3}{4(n + z_{\alpha/2}^2 - 1)w^2} \right] + K$$

$$W_3 = \frac{n}{n + z_{\alpha/2}^2 - 1}$$

$$K = \frac{W_3 (1 - 2\hat{\pi}_{yes})^2}{4z_{\alpha/2}^4 w^2}$$

2.2.3 Shan's Exact Confidence Interval

Shan (2016) proposed exact confidence intervals for randomized response strategies by adjusting the critical values used in Frey and Pérez (2012) and Chang and Kuo (2012) to ensure nominal coverage probabilities across the entire parameter space. Shan (2016) observed that the use of asymptotic critical values, such as the normal quantile $z_{\alpha/2}$ in Chang and Kuo (2012) and the LRT statistic $\chi_{\alpha,1}^2$ in Frey and Pérez (2012), can lead to low coverage probabilities for certain values of π . To address this, Shan proposed the following condition:

$$\inf_{\pi \in (0,1)} \sum_X P(\pi \in CI_\zeta(X)) \geq 1 - \alpha,$$

where $CI_\zeta(X)$ represents the confidence interval for observed data X that ensures a minimum desired coverage level of $1 - \alpha$ and $\zeta \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ for Wilson-type confidence intervals and $\zeta = \text{LR}$ for confidence intervals due to Frey and Pérez (2012). To guarantee the desired coverage, this approach relies on simulations to determine the critical value C_{LR} for the LRT that replaces the critical value $\chi_{\alpha,1}^2$ in the confidence interval and C_1, C_2, C_3 for the Wilson-type confidence intervals that replace the critical value $z_{\alpha/2}$ in Chang and Kuo (2012).

The only modifications in the first, second, and third Wilson-type confidence intervals of Shan (2016) are the replacements of $z_{\alpha/2}$ by C_1, C_2 , and C_3 , respectively. However, we noted that in the third Wilson-type confidence interval, $W_3 = \frac{n}{n+C_1^2-1}$, which depends on the critical value from the first Wilson-type interval critical value, C_1 . For Frey and Pérez (2012), the only modification made is the replacement of $\chi_{\alpha,1}^2$ by C_{LR} . In addition, Shan (2016) and Chang and Kuo (2012) directly find the confidence interval for π from the observed π_{yes} as shown in Section 2.2.2. However, in Frey and Pérez (2012), to find the confidence interval for π , the transformation of the initial interval for π_{yes} , denoted as $(L(X), U(X))$, is transformed to obtain the exact confidence interval for π :

$$(L'(X), U'(X)) = \left(\frac{L(X) - v}{w}, \frac{U(X) - v}{w} \right).$$

According to Shan (2016), their method achieves better coverage by adjusting critical values – denoted as C_1, C_2, C_3 , and C_{LR} . However, the simulation

code used to determine these values is not available, so we omit numerical coverage comparisons for this method. Nevertheless, the balance achieved between the interval length and coverage makes this approach particularly appealing and suitable for randomized response surveys that address sensitive data, and we invite the reader to explore this method.

3 Tolerance Intervals

The development of tolerance intervals dates back to the foundational works by [Wilks \(1941, 1942\)](#) and [Wald \(1943\)](#). Comprehensive treatments of their theoretical foundations and applications can be found in the texts of [Guttman \(1970\)](#) and [Krishnamoorthy and Mathew \(2009\)](#). The computation of tolerance intervals and regions under various distributional assumptions and sampling contexts can be accomplished using the R package `tolerance` by [Young \(2010\)](#). Beyond these important contributions to tolerance intervals, there are numerous works highlighting their broad practical utility. In industrial quality control settings, [von Collani and Baur \(2002\)](#) examined how they are used to perform interventions for assuring a desired quality level as well as to meet certain specifications, such as those established by regulatory agencies. In one of their few applications to survey methodology, [Young and Mathew \(2015\)](#) used tolerance intervals to define ratio edit tolerance regions that improve data quality by managing error rates. In the area of laboratory medicine, [Young and Mathew \(2020\)](#) developed multivariate tolerance regions to construct reference regions for laboratory test results, thus supporting more informed clinical

decision making.

Formally, statistical tolerance intervals provide bounds within which a specified proportion or content – denoted by P – of the population is expected to fall, with a given level of confidence. It is helpful to first discuss the formal definition of univariate statistical tolerance intervals in the context of continuous data. Let $\mathbf{X} = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n)$ be a random sample drawn from a continuous distribution with cumulative distribution function F_{θ} , parameterized by $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$. Assume $X \sim F_{\theta}$, independently of \mathbf{X} . A one-sided upper $(1 - \alpha, P)$ tolerance limit $U_1(\mathbf{X})$ and a one-sided $(1 - \alpha, P)$ lower tolerance limit $L_1(\mathbf{X})$ are defined by the following conditions:

$$P_{\mathbf{X}}(P_X[X \leq U_1(\mathbf{X}) \mid \mathbf{X}] \geq P) = 1 - \alpha, \quad (2)$$

$$P_{\mathbf{X}}(P_X[L_1(\mathbf{X}) \leq X \mid \mathbf{X}] \geq P) = 1 - \alpha. \quad (3)$$

For a two-sided $(1 - \alpha, P)$ tolerance interval with bounds $(L_2(\mathbf{X}), U_2(\mathbf{X}))$, the requirement becomes:

$$P_{\mathbf{X}}(P_X[L_2(\mathbf{X}) \leq X \leq U_2(\mathbf{X}) \mid \mathbf{X}] \geq P) = 1 - \alpha. \quad (4)$$

Finally, symmetry in terms of the content in each tail can be achieved using an equal-tailed tolerance interval $(L_e(\mathbf{X}), U_e(\mathbf{X}))$. This interval satisfies the following:

$$P_{\mathbf{X}}\left(\left\{P_X[L_e(\mathbf{X}) \leq X \mid \mathbf{X}] \leq \frac{1-P}{2}\right\} \cap \left\{P_X[U_e(\mathbf{X}) \geq X \mid \mathbf{X}] \leq \frac{1-P}{2}\right\}\right) = 1 - \alpha. \quad (5)$$

The above definitions ensure that for any of the intervals $[L, U]$, we can say with $100(1-\alpha)\%$ confidence that at least $100P\%$ of the population lies between the limits.

We note that, for example, the method of [Frey and Pérez \(2012\)](#) is based on a framework of n “yes” and “no” responses that are Bernoulli trials where the probabilities π and π_{Yes} satisfy a relationship $\pi_{\text{Yes}} = f(\pi)$ for some invertible monotone function $f(\cdot)$. As emphasized by [Frey and Pérez \(2012\)](#), their intervals can be used with randomized response schemes that are based on simple random sampling with replacement, but not with schemes that use more complicated designs. Hence, their framework can utilize binomial confidence intervals. In the present work, we leverage a way to construct approximate tolerance intervals for discrete distributions due to [Hahn and Chandra \(1981\)](#), which has become the classic approach for tolerance intervals for binomial and Poisson random variables. While the Warner-type methods in [Section 2.1](#) do not have the same assumptions as that in [Frey and Pérez \(2012\)](#), we consider the construction of binomial tolerance intervals for RRTs, but based on the confidence intervals constructed for the Warner-type methods in [Section 2.1](#) and the universal methods in [Section 2.2](#). We now discuss the procedure due to [Hahn and Chandra \(1981\)](#), but in the context of tolerance interval construction for these RRTs.

3.1 Tolerance Intervals for RRTs

Let $X \sim \text{Bin}(n, \pi)$, where in our RRT framework, n is the number of individuals in our survey and π retains its interpretation of the true proportion

of individuals with the sensitive attribute. Letting $F(\cdot|\pi, n)$ denote the corresponding cumulative distribution function, we know that for a fixed n , $F(\cdot|\pi, n)$ is increasing stochastically in π ; i.e., $\Pr(X > t|\pi_1) \geq \Pr(X > t|\pi_2)$ for $\pi_1 > \pi_2$. The construction of binomial tolerance intervals using the method due to [Hahn and Chandra \(1981\)](#) involves two key steps:

1. Based on the observed x (i.e., those subjects who responded “yes”), construct a two-sided $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ confidence interval for the parameter π using any of the methods presented in Section 2. Denote this confidence interval as $(\pi_{L_2}(x; n), \pi_{U_2}(x; n))$.
2. For a future survey of m individuals an RRT, find the smallest integer $L_2(x; m)$ and largest integer $U_2(x; m)$, such that, respectively

$$1 - F(L_2(x; m) | \pi_{L_2}(x; n), m) \geq \frac{1 + P}{2}$$

and

$$F(U_2(x; m) | U_2(x; m), m) \geq \frac{1 + P}{2}.$$

Thus, the above tolerance interval will give you, with $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ confidence, where at least $100P\%$ of the distribution of the number of individuals with the sensitive attribute in surveys of m respondents fall. Note also that the above construction is an equal-tailed tolerance interval.

The construction of one-sided tolerance intervals using the above method is simply done by replacing the content expression $(1 + P)/2$ by P and replacing the two-sided limits of $\pi_{L_2}(x; n)$ and $\pi_{U_2}(x; n)$ by, respectively, the one-sided

lower limit $\pi_{L_2}(x; n)$ and the one-sided upper limit $\pi_{U_2}(x; n)$. Thus, a one-sided lower $(1 - \alpha, P)$ tolerance limit $L_1(x; m)$ is the smallest integer such that

$$1 - F(L_1(x; m) \mid \pi_{L_1}(x; n), m) \geq P$$

and a one-sided upper $(1 - \alpha, P)$ tolerance limit $U_1(x; m)$ is the largest integer such that

$$F(U_1(x; m) \mid \pi_{U_1}(x; n), m) \geq P.$$

4 Coverage Study

For our numerical study, we employ similar coverage studies as those by [Krishnamoorthy et al. \(2011\)](#) (for binomial and Poisson tolerance intervals) and [Young \(2014\)](#) (for negative binomial tolerance intervals), to construct the binomial tolerance intervals using the method presented in [Section 3.1](#). Our goal is to examine the empirical coverage of our tolerance intervals in different RRT settings.

The traditional approach to studying a coverage probability for statistical intervals is heavily based on Monte Carlo simulations. Typically, these simulations involve generating a large number of random samples from a given population and computing confidence or tolerance intervals for each sample. The proportion of these intervals that contain the true population parameter gives an estimate of the probability of coverage. In contrast, [Krishnamoorthy et al. \(2011\)](#) used an approximate analytical approach for coverages of tolerance intervals based on the confidence intervals for the parameter of interest.

This circumvents extensive simulations while maintaining accuracy. Evaluation of the coverage probabilities for the equal-tailed tolerance intervals for our RRT setting uses the following consistent with [Krishnamoorthy et al. \(2011\)](#):

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \pi^k (1-\pi)^{n-k} \mathbf{I} \left\{ L_2(x; m, \pi_{L_2}) \geq \omega_{(1+P)/2; \pi, m} \cap U_2(x; m, \pi_{U_2}) \leq \omega_{(1-P)/2; \pi, m} \right\} \quad (6)$$

where $L_2(x; m, \pi_{L_2})$ and $U_2(x; m, \pi_{U_2})$ are again the lower and upper limits for the two-sided $(1 - \alpha, P)$ tolerance interval, but written to show their dependency on the RRT confidence interval limits, and $\omega_{q; \pi, m}$ is the q^{th} quantile from a binomial distribution with probability of success π and sample size m . The above equation ensures that the interval captures the required proportion P of the population with a confidence level $1 - \alpha$. The formula in Equation (6) is also easily modified to perform the coverage probabilities for the one-sided lower and one-sided upper settings.

One aspect to note are some of the coverage behaviors for discrete distributions as addressed in [Cai and Wang \(2009\)](#). First, oscillations in coverage probabilities due to the lattice structure of some discrete distributions, like the binomial and Poisson, are unavoidable in any non-randomized procedure. [Cai and Wang \(2009\)](#) also noted that systematic biases in tolerance intervals can be larger than expected in certain settings. A remedy for such behaviors is very challenging to address, including the quite extensive correction method derived in [Cai and Wang \(2009\)](#), which is only addressed for specific discrete distributional settings.

We first consider two settings for our coverage study. In both settings,

we use $p = 0.75$, $P = 0.95$, and $\alpha = 0.05$, but look at two different sample sizes: $n = 40$ and $n = 80$. Table 4.1 presents the mean, minimum, median, and standard deviation of coverage probabilities for the different RRT models when $n = 40$. We observe that Horvitz and Soberanis-Cruz models show the highest mean coverage probabilities, closely followed by the Devore and Warner models. However, models such as Singh-Joarder and Mangat-Singh-Singh exhibit slightly lower mean values and higher standard deviations, indicating more variability in coverage probabilities. Similarly, Table 4.2 reports results for the $n = 80$ setting, where the Horvitz and Soberanis-Cruz models again maintain high mean coverage probabilities, but with a reduced standard deviation compared to $n = 40$. This highlights the impact of a larger sample size on somewhat reducing the conservatism of the coverage probabilities.

Table 4.1: Two-sided Tolerance Interval Coverage Results for RRT Models ($n = 40$)

Model	Mean	Min	Median	SD
Warner	0.9788	0.9434	0.9848	0.0149
Singh-Joarder	0.9682	0.9358	0.9639	0.0165
Devore	0.9812	0.9574	0.9842	0.0106
Horvitz	0.9854	0.9651	0.9851	0.0077
Soberanis-Cruz	0.9847	0.9598	0.9835	0.0093
Mangat-Singh-Singh	0.9682	0.9358	0.9639	0.0165
Frey-Perez	0.9821	0.9651	0.9835	0.0066
Chang-Kuo #1	0.9653	0.9434	0.9652	0.0091
Chang-Kuo #2	0.9664	0.9293	0.9701	0.0111
Chang-Kuo #3	0.9728	0.9426	0.9741	0.0097

While the coverage results in Tables 4.1 and 4.2 provide valuable numerical summaries, it is crucial to recognize their limitations. Reporting only the

Table 4.2: Two-sided Tolerance Interval Coverage Results for RRT Models ($n = 80$)

Model	Mean	Min	Median	SD
Warner	0.9742	0.9434	0.9815	0.0162
Singh-Joarder	0.9622	0.9280	0.9578	0.0157
Devore	0.9781	0.9540	0.9787	0.0101
Horvitz	0.9811	0.9664	0.9794	0.0083
Soberanis-Cruz	0.9836	0.9687	0.9820	0.0080
Mangat-Singh-Singh	0.9622	0.9280	0.9578	0.0157
Frey-Perez	0.9731	0.9644	0.9718	0.0055
Chang-Kuo #1	0.9617	0.9439	0.9614	0.0077
Chang-Kuo #2	0.9626	0.9393	0.9639	0.0079
Chang-Kuo #3	0.9738	0.9434	0.9731	0.0126

mean and standard deviation of coverage probabilities does not reveal how coverage fluctuates across different true probability values. A method that consistently covers the true parameter but has large variability might appear misleadingly stable when summarized using only these statistics. Essentially, we could be observing coverage performance relative to “lucky” or “unlucky” combinations of n and p , a phenomenon addressed in the extensive review of binomial proportion confidence intervals by [Brown et al. \(2001\)](#). Moreover, the minimum and median values may obscure whether the method is systematically conservative or anti-conservative. If certain methods have coverage oscillations, this can only be observed through detailed plots. To properly assess performance across a fine grid of randomized response probabilities, we explore different scenarios using empirical coverage probability plots. The scenarios are outlined as follows:

- **Scenario 1:** The sample size is varied for $n \in \{40, 80, 160, 320\}$ while

keeping the other parameters fixed at $P = 0.95$, $\alpha = 0.05$, and $p = 0.75$.

- **Scenario 2:** Different content levels, $P \in \{0.90, 0.95\}$, and different confidence levels, $(1 - \alpha) \in \{0.90, 0.95\}$, are assessed at a fixed sample size of $n = 80$.
- **Scenario 3:** The randomized response probability is varied, $p \in \{0.70, 0.75, 0.80, 0.85\}$, while maintaining a two-sided interval ($\text{side} = 2$) at a fixed sample size of $n = 80$.
- **Scenario 4:** This focuses on the performance of the methods due to [Frey and Pérez \(2012\)](#) by varying the values of a_1 and a_2 for the constrained case.
- **Scenario 5:** This focuses on the models due to [Greenberg et al. \(1969\)](#), [Soberanis-Cruz et al. \(2008\)](#), and [Singh et al. \(1995\)](#), where the probability of unrelated questions, π_U , is varied.

The above scenarios are designed to systematically evaluate how different parameter choices affect the reliability and accuracy of tolerance intervals in randomized response models.

In Section 2, we separated the different RRT methods into two categories: Warner-type methods (Section 2.1) and universal methods (Section 2.2). For the purpose of the following summaries, we will split the Warner-type methods into two categories: one that we refer to as Warner methods and another as unrelated questions methods. Specifically, the Warner methods includes [Warner \(1965\)](#), [Devore \(1977\)](#), and [Singh and Joarder \(1997\)](#), the unrelated questions

methods includes [Greenberg et al. \(1969\)](#), [Soberanis-Cruz et al. \(2008\)](#), and [Singh et al. \(1995\)](#), and the universal methods includes [Frey and Pérez \(2012\)](#), [Chang and Kuo \(2012\)](#), and [Shan \(2016\)](#). We note that the name “universal” comes from the fact that these three models can be used to construct confidence intervals and tolerance intervals for any type of RRT used in sampling.

We note that all coverage calculations in the following summary are conducted using two-sided equal-tailed tolerance intervals. However, similar procedures can be applied to compute coverages for one-sided tolerance intervals, whether upper or lower, using the same approach.

4.1 Warner Methods

We briefly summarize coverage results for the method due to [Warner \(1965\)](#), while the coverage results from [Devore \(1977\)](#) and [Singh and Joarder \(1997\)](#) are provided in [Appendix A](#). The results of our simulation are illustrated in [Figures 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3](#). Each plot demonstrates the empirical coverage probability as a function of the true probability π , providing information on the performance of tolerance intervals under different conditions.

[Figure 4.1](#) shows the coverage probabilities for different sample sizes. The plots indicate that smaller sample sizes tend to exhibit more variability in coverage, while larger samples stabilize around the nominal level. [Figure 4.2](#) presents the impact of different values of P and α on coverage probability. As expected, lower confidence levels result in slightly wider variability, particularly near the middle range of π . Finally, [Figure 4.3](#) illustrates how the randomized response probability p affects the tolerance interval performance. Increasing p

slightly reduces coverage variability, suggesting that optimizing p can improve interval accuracy. While they are not included, Singh and Joarder (1997) and Devore (1977) simulations are similar to Warner (1965) method, but with slightly better coverage.

Figure 4.1: Scenario 1: Coverage Probability Across Different Sample Sizes for the Warner Method

Figure 4.2: Scenario 2: Coverage Probability for Different Values of P and α in the Warner Method

Figure 4.3: Scenario 3: Coverage Probability for Different Values of p and Interval Side

4.2 Unrelated Questions Methods

We next summarize coverage results for the method of [Greenberg et al. \(1969\)](#), while the results for the methods of [Soberanis-Cruz et al. \(2008\)](#) and [Singh et al. \(1995\)](#) are provided in Appendix B. The method due to [Greenberg et al. \(1969\)](#), based on the unrelated question model proposed by [Greenberg et al. \(1969\)](#), provides an alternative RRT to improve the privacy of the respondent while estimating the true prevalence of sensitive characteristics. Unlike the classic method of [Warner \(1965\)](#), which relies on direct randomization, the Horvitz approach uses an unrelated question to introduce randomness.

Figure 4.4 illustrates the impact of sample size on coverage probability using Horvitz's method. Similar to Warner's method, smaller sample sizes exhibit greater variability, while larger sample sizes lead to more stable coverage probabilities. Figure 4.5 examines the sensitivity of coverage probability to different confidence levels and content levels. The results indicate that increasing

α leads to a broader range of coverage probabilities, particularly in the middle values of π , where the randomized response mechanism has the greatest influence. Figure 4.6 investigates the effect of varying the probability p in the Horvitz method. Lower values of p introduce more variability in the coverage probability, whereas higher values of p stabilize coverage. Finally, Scenario 4 is summarized in Figure 4.7, which explores the influence of π_U , the probability associated with the unrelated question. As expected, increasing π_U introduces additional uncertainty into the randomized response mechanism, affecting the resulting coverage probabilities.

Figure 4.4: Scenario 1: Coverage Probability Across Different Sample Sizes for the Horvitz Method

4.3 Universal Methods

We now investigate the method proposed by Chang and Kuo (2012), with additional results provided in Appendix C. The results of the simulation in Figures 4.8, 4.9, and 4.10, focus on the first estimator. Each plot demon-

Figure 4.5: Scenario 2: Coverage Probability for Different Values of P and α in the Horvitz Method

Figure 4.6: Scenario 3: Coverage Probability for Different Values of p and Interval Side in the Horvitz Method

strates the empirical coverage probability as a function of the true probability π , providing insights into the performance of tolerance intervals under different conditions. Like Frey and Pérez (2012) and Shan (2016), the Chang-Kuo methods are universal in the sense that they can be used to construct both

Figure 4.7: Scenario 4: Coverage Probability for Different Values of π_U in the Horvitz Method

confidence intervals and tolerance intervals. While we do not have a dedicated coverage study performed for the methods of Frey and Pérez (2012), those authors demonstrated that their method improves exact confidence intervals in randomized response models. Additionally, Shan (2016) showed that their approach enhances previous RRTs and specifically improves the coverage performance of the Chang-Kuo method.

Figure 4.8 shows the coverage probabilities for different sample sizes. The plots indicate that smaller sample sizes tend to exhibit more variability in coverage, while larger sample sizes stabilize around the nominal level. This is consistent with the results in Tables 4.1 and 4.2, which quantify how sample size influences the empirical coverage probability.

Figure 4.9 presents the impact of different values of P and α on the coverage probability. As expected, lower confidence levels result in slightly wider variability, particularly near the middle range of π . This aligns with previous

Figure 4.8: Scenario 1: Coverage Probability Across Different Sample Sizes for the Chang-Kuo #1 Method

Figure 4.9: Scenario 2: Coverage Probability for Different Values of P and α in the Chang-Kuo #1 Method

findings by [Shan \(2016\)](#), who demonstrated improvements in coverage accuracy compared to earlier RRTs.

Finally, [Figure 4.10](#) highlights the performance of the [Chang and Kuo \(2012\)](#) method under different values of parameters v and w , demonstrating

Figure 4.10: Scenario 5: Two-Sided Tolerance Intervals for Different v and w Values in Chang-Kuo #1 Method

how these choices affect the coverage probability. Note that v and w will depend on which RRT method is used. For our work, we assume that the RRT used was Warner's model. This further supports the generalization that the Chang-Kuo models can be effectively used for constructing both tolerance and confidence intervals.

5 Application: Academic Cheating Study

We consider an example of a randomized response survey conducted by [Quatember \(2009\)](#) to estimate the proportion of students engaging in academic cheating. The study involved $n = 80$ students, each responding using a randomized response mechanism. Each respondent answered "yes" based on a probability mechanism involving dice rolls, ensuring confidentiality while estimating the cheating proportion π . Out of 80 responses, 63 were recorded as "yes," leading

to an MLE of $\hat{\pi} = 0.716$.

To assess the effectiveness of various tolerance interval methods, we analyze different approaches applied in the study. Tables 5.1 and 5.2 summarize comparisons across different methods. The results reveal key differences in the resulting tolerance intervals. For one-sided tolerance intervals (Table 5.1), Warner’s method yields the widest intervals, while the Mangat-Singh-Singh approach provides narrower intervals with similar coverage probabilities. The results of the two-sided intervals in Appendix D indicate that methods such as the Horvitz method and Soberanis-Cruz method offer pragmatic interval widths while maintaining strong coverage as shown in the earlier coverage study.

Table 5.1: Tolerance Intervals for Different Methods with side = 1, $\alpha = 0.05$, $P = .95$

Method	$\hat{\pi}$	vâr	Lower π	Upper π	1-Sided Lower	1-Sided Upper
Warner	1.00000	0.01187	0.78649	1.00000	57	80
Singh-Joarder	0.78182	0.00448	0.65061	0.91303	45	77
Devore	0.71667	0.00596	0.5654	0.86793	38	74
Horvitz*	0.71667	0.00573	0.56826	0.86507	38	74
Soberanis-Cruz*	0.71667	0.00506	0.57724	0.85609	39	73
Mangat-Singh-Singh*	0.71667	0.00377	0.59639	0.83694	40	72
Frey	0.7875	–	0.5768	0.82909	39	72
ChangKuo1	0.6991	0.00363	0.58104	0.81717	39	71
ChangKuo2	0.6781	0.00449	0.54672	0.80952	36	70
ChangKuo3	0.70352	0.01232	0.48599	0.92104	32	77

*Model based on Unrelated Question assuming $\pi_U = 1.0$

When adjusting the confidence level to $1 - \alpha = 0.90$ (see Appendix D), a noticeable shift occurs in that some methods, such as Frey-Perez and Chang-Kuo #1, maintain relatively narrow bounds. Using $1 - \alpha = 0.90$ in a two-sided setting also has increased interval width, especially in methods with higher

variance estimates.

Table 5.2: Tolerance Intervals for Different Methods with side = 2, $\alpha = 0.10$, $P = .95$

Method	$\hat{\pi}$	$\hat{v}\text{ar}$	Lower π	Upper π	2-Sided Lower	2-Sided Upper
Warner	1.0000	0.01187	0.78649	1.0000	55	80
Singh-Joarder	0.78182	0.00448	0.65061	0.91303	44	78
Devore	0.71667	0.00596	0.56540	0.86793	37	75
Horvitz*	0.71667	0.00573	0.56826	0.86507	37	75
Soberanis-Cruz*	0.71667	0.00506	0.57724	0.85609	37	74
Mangat-Singh-Singh*	0.71667	0.00377	0.59639	0.83694	39	73
Frey	0.7875	—	0.5768	0.82909	37	73
ChangKuo1	0.6991	0.00363	0.581041	0.81717	38	72
ChangKuo2	0.67812	0.00449	0.54672	0.80952	35	71
ChangKuo3	0.70352	0.01232	0.48599	0.92104	30	78

*Model based on Unrelated Question assuming $\pi_U = 1.0$

For different content levels P , we see that when $P = 0.90$, the tolerance intervals become slightly narrower compared to $P = 0.95$, as seen in Appendix D. Notably, Shan's methods tend to produce wider intervals, whereas the Chang-Kuo and Soberanis-Cruz methods offer narrower intervals coupled with the stronger coverage results of the methods noted earlier.

5.1 Interpretation of Tolerance Intervals

For this application, it is helpful to emphasize the interpretation of the tolerance limits that are calculated. We interpret those obtained using Warner's method.

First, we have the results for the two-sided (0.90, 0.95) tolerance interval, which are given below from the R routine developed for this work:

```
> bintol.int(z=63,n=80,p=0.75,alpha=0.05,P = 0.95, side = 2,method="warner")
  Method alpha    P pi_hat var_hat lower.yes upper.yes lower.pi upper.pi 2-sided.lower 2-sided.upper
1 warner  0.05 0.95      1  0.0119   0.6279   0.8721   0.7558          1           53          80
```

These results mean we are 95% confident that at least 95% of all surveys with samples of size $n = 80$ using the Warner randomized response design will estimate that the number of individuals in Group A (those who cheated) to fall between 53 and 80. Thus, if we were to conduct many randomized response surveys using the Warner method, at least 95% of them would result in an estimated proportion of individuals in Group A within this range.

Next we have the results for the one-sided $(0.90, 0.95)$ lower tolerance limit:

```
> bintol.int(z=63,n=80,p=0.75,alpha=0.05,P = 0.95, side = 1,method="warner")
  Method alpha    P pi_hat var_hat lower.yes upper.yes lower.pi upper.pi 1-sided.lower 1-sided.upper
1 warner  0.05 0.95      1  0.0119   0.6432   0.8568   0.7865      1           57           80
```

These results mean we are 95% confident that at least 95% of all randomized response surveys conducted using the Warner randomized response design will estimate the number of individuals in Group A (those who cheated) to be at least 57. A lower one-sided tolerance interval ensures that the estimate does not fall below a certain threshold, which is particularly useful in settings where a minimum guarantee may be required. Similar reasoning applies for a one-sided upper tolerance limit.

6 Conclusion

This paper introduced a strategy for constructing tolerance intervals in randomized response models, leveraging a tolerance interval methods due to [Hahn and Chandra \(1981\)](#) and numerous confidence intervals that have appeared in the randomized response literature. Based on an empirical coverage study,

it was observed that all methods investigated demonstrate some level of conservativeness, though to varying degrees. The Mangat-Singh-Singh method achieves moderate conservativeness with good coverage performance. The approach based on Chang-Kuo asymptotic confidence intervals provide a balance between precision, coverage, and computational efficiency. The Frey-Perez method is more conservative, but with lower variability in the coverages. Warner's method has the highest variability in terms of its coverage probability. These findings indicate that each method has its strengths and trade-offs depending on the priorities in tolerance interval construction, whether it be precision, coverage probability, or computational efficiency. Finally, we also applied the approach to a survey on academic cheating and provided interpretation of the resulting tolerance limits.

While our study has provided a broad overview of tolerance interval construction for randomized response designs, there are some potential directions for future research. In particular, our work focused on simple RRTs that yield binary outcomes under simple random sampling with replacement (SRSWR). Future work can extend the analysis to other sampling methods, such as simple random sampling without replacement (SRSWOR), where the population size N is known. Alternative RRTs for such sampling designs are detailed in the RRTCS package by [Rodríguez et al. \(2022\)](#) and in the book by [Chaudhuri \(2011\)](#). Such extensions would broaden the utility of tolerance intervals as it pertains to randomized response designs.

Acknowledgements

We are very thankful to Professor Jesse Frey for providing us with updated R code corresponding to [Frey and Pérez \(2012\)](#).

A Additional Simulation Results for the Warner Methods

This appendix presents supplementary results that illustrate the performance of tolerance intervals for different parameter settings in the Singh-Joarder and Devore methods. Figures A.1–A.3 explore the effects of varying sample sizes, significance levels, and probability values on the coverage probabilities for the Singh-Joarder method. Similarly, Figures A.4–A.6 provide the corresponding results for the Devore method. These visualizations help compare the robustness and accuracy of each method under different conditions as discussed in Section 4.1.

Figure A.1: Different Sample Sizes for Singh-Joarder Method

Figure A.2: Different P and α Values for Singh-Joarder Method

Figure A.3: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different Probabilities of Randomized Response, p , for Singh-Joarder Method

Figure A.4: Different Sample Sizes for Devore Method

Figure A.5: Different P and α for Devore Method

Figure A.6: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different Probabilities of Randomized Response, p , for Devore Method

B Additional Simulation Results for the Unrelated Questions Methods

This appendix presents supplementary results that illustrate the performance of tolerance intervals for different parameter settings in the Mangat-Singh-Singh and Soberanis-Cruz methods. Figures B.1–B.4 explore the effects of varying sample sizes, significance levels, probability values, and upper bound π_U on the coverage probabilities for the Mangat-Singh-Singh method. Similarly, Figures B.5–B.8 provide the corresponding results for the Soberanis-Cruz method. These visualizations help compare the robustness and accuracy of each method under different conditions, as discussed in Section 4.2.

Figure B.1: Different Sample Sizes for Mangat-Singh-Singh Method

Figure B.2: Different P and α Values for Mangat-Singh-Singh Method

Figure B.3: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different Probabilities of Randomized Response, p , for Mangat-Singh-Singh Method

Figure B.4: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different Upper Bound π_U Values for Mangat-Singh-Singh Method

Figure B.5: Different Sample Sizes for Soberanis-Cruz Method

Figure B.6: Different P and α Values for Soberanis-Cruz Method

Figure B.7: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different Probabilities of Randomized Response, p , for Soberanis-Cruz Method

Figure B.8: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different Upper Bound π_U Values for Soberanis-Cruz Method

C Additional Simulation Results for the Universal Methods

This appendix presents supplementary results that illustrate the performance of tolerance intervals for different parameter settings in the Chang-Kuo models. Figures C.1–C.4 explore the effects of varying sample sizes, significance levels, probability values, and response parameters v and w on coverage probabilities for the Chang-Kuo #2 method. Similarly, Figures C.5–C.8 provide the corresponding results for the Chang-Kuo #3 method. These visualizations help compare the robustness and accuracy of each method under different conditions, as discussed in Section 4.3.

Figure C.1: Different Sample Sizes for Chang-Kuo #2 Method

Figure C.2: Different P and α Values for Chang-Kuo #2 Method

Figure C.3: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different Probabilities of Randomized Response, p , for Chang-Kuo #2 Method

Figure C.4: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different v and w Values for Chang-Kuo #2 Method

Figure C.5: Different Sample Sizes for Chang-Kuo #3 Method

Figure C.6: Different P and α Values for Chang-Kuo #3 Method

Figure C.7: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different Probabilities of Randomized Response, p , for Chang-Kuo #3 Method

Figure C.8: Two-sided Tolerance Intervals for Different v and w Values for Chang-Kuo #3 Method

D Additional Tolerance Interval Results for the Data Application

Tables D.1–D.6 supplement the application in Section 5 and provide comparison of different randomized response models in constructing tolerance intervals under various conditions. Each table reports the estimated proportion ($\hat{\pi}$), variance estimates, and interval bounds across multiple methods, including Warner, Singh-Joarder, Devore, and newer methods like Frey-Perez, Chang-Kuo, and Shan. Models based on unrelated question assumptions are indicated by an asterisk (*).

Table D.1: Tolerance Intervals for Different Methods with $side = 2, \alpha = 0.05, P = .95$

Method	$\hat{\pi}$	\hat{var}	Lower π	Upper π	2-Sided Lower	2-Sided Upper
Warner	1.0000	0.01187	0.75583	1.0000	53	80
Singh-Joarder	0.78182	0.00448	0.63177	0.93187	42	78
Devore	0.71667	0.00596	0.54368	0.88966	35	76
Horvitz*	0.71667	0.00573	0.54695	0.88638	35	76
Soberanis-Cruz*	0.71667	0.00506	0.55722	0.87611	36	75
Mangat-Singh-Singh*	0.71667	0.00377	0.57912	0.85421	38	74
Frey	0.7875	–	0.55694	0.84147	36	73
ChangKuo1	0.69402	0.0036	0.55951	0.82852	36	73
ChangKuo2	0.67812	0.00449	0.52785	0.82838	33	73
ChangKuo3	0.69831	0.00845	0.49232	0.9043	31	77
Shan1	0.6048	0.00301	0.28965	0.91997	15	78
Shan2	0.6781	0.00449	0.32003	1.00000	18	80
Shan3	0.6878	0.0055	0.48453	0.89107	30	76

*Model based on Unrelated Question assuming $\pi_U = 1$

Table D.2: Tolerance Intervals for Different Methods with side = 1, $\alpha = 0.10$, $P = .95$

Method	$\hat{\pi}$	$\hat{v}\text{ar}$	Lower π	Upper π	1-Sided Lower	1-Sided Upper
Warner	1.00000	0.01187	0.82082	1.00000	60	80
Singh-Joarder	0.78182	0.00448	0.67170	0.89193	47	76
Devore	0.71667	0.00596	0.58972	0.84361	40	73
Horvitz*	0.71667	0.00573	0.59212	0.84121	40	72
Soberanis-Cruz*	0.71667	0.00506	0.59966	0.83368	41	72
Mangat-Singh-Singh*	0.71667	0.00377	0.61573	0.81761	42	71
Frey	0.7875	—	0.59918	0.81424	41	71
ChangKuo1	0.70413	0.00366	0.60468	0.80357	41	70
ChangKuo2	0.67812	0.00449	0.56785	0.78839	38	69
ChangKuo3	0.70866	0.02197	0.46484	0.95249	30	79
Shan1	0.61302	0.00308	0.31106	0.91498	18	77
Shan2	0.67812	0.00449	0.36002	0.99621	22	80
Shan3	0.70016	0.00949	0.49123	0.90909	32	77

*Model based on Unrelated Question assuming $\pi_U = 1$

Table D.3: Tolerance Intervals for Different Methods with side = 1, $\alpha = 0.05$, $P = 0.90$

Method	$\hat{\pi}$	$\hat{v}\text{ar}$	Lower π	Upper π	1-Sided Lower	1-Sided Upper
Warner	1.00000	0.01187	0.78649	1.00000	58	80
Singh-Joarder	0.78182	0.00448	0.65061	0.91303	47	76
Devore	0.71667	0.00596	0.5654	0.86793	40	73
Horvitz*	0.71667	0.00573	0.56826	0.86507	40	73
Soberanis-Cruz*	0.71667	0.00506	0.57724	0.85609	41	72
Mangat-Singh-Singh*	0.71667	0.00377	0.59639	0.83694	42	71
Frey	0.7875	—	0.5768	0.82909	40	71
ChangKuo1	0.6991	0.00363	0.58104	0.81717	41	70
ChangKuo2	0.67812	0.00449	0.54672	0.80952	38	69
ChangKuo3	0.70352	0.01232	0.48599	0.92104	33	77
Shan1	0.60983	0.00305	0.30269	0.91696	19	76
Shan1	0.67812	0.00449	0.33219	1.00000	21	80
Shan1	0.6939	0.00678	0.49135	0.89645	34	75

*Model based on Unrelated Question assuming $\pi_U = 1.0$

Table D.4: Tolerance Intervals for Different Methods with side = 2, $\alpha = 0.05$, $P = .90$

Method	$\hat{\pi}$	vâr	Lower π	Upper π	2-Sided Lower	2-Sided Upper
Warner	1.0000	0.01187	0.75583	1.0000	54	80
Singh-Joarder	0.78182	0.00448	0.63177	0.93187	43	78
Devore	0.71667	0.00596	0.54368	0.88966	36	76
Horvitz*	0.71667	0.00573	0.54695	0.88638	37	75
Soberanis-Cruz*	0.71667	0.00506	0.55722	0.87611	37	75
Mangat-Singh-Singh*	0.71667	0.00377	0.57912	0.85421	39	73
Frey	0.7875	—	0.55694	0.84147	37	72
ChangKuo1	0.69402	0.00360	0.55951	0.82852	37	72
ChangKuo2	0.67812	0.00449	0.52785	0.82838	35	72
ChangKuo3	0.69831	0.00845	0.49232	0.90430	32	76
Shan1	0.60481	0.00301	0.28965	0.91997	17	77
Shan3	0.67812	0.00449	0.32003	1.00000	19	80
Shan3	0.6878	0.0055	0.48453	0.89107	31	76

*Model based on Unrelated Question assuming $\pi_U = 1.0$ Table D.5: Tolerance Intervals for Different Methods with side = 1, $\alpha = 0.10$, $P = 0.90$

Method	$\hat{\pi}$	vâr	Lower π	Upper π	1-Sided Lower	1-Sided Upper
Warner	1.00000	0.01187	0.82082	1.00000	61	80
Singh-Joarder	0.78182	0.00448	0.6717	0.89193	48	75
Devore	0.71667	0.00596	0.58972	0.84361	42	72
Horvitz*	0.71667	0.00573	0.59212	0.84121	42	71
Soberanis-Cruz*	0.71667	0.00506	0.59966	0.83368	42	71
Mangat-Singh-Singh*	0.71667	0.00377	0.61573	0.81761	44	70
Frey	0.7875	—	0.59918	0.81424	42	70
ChangKuo1	0.70413	0.00366	0.60468	0.80357	43	69
ChangKuo2	0.67812	0.00449	0.56785	0.78839	40	68
ChangKuo3	0.70866	0.02197	0.46484	0.95249	31	79
Shan1	0.61302	0.00305	0.31106	0.91498	20	76
Shan1	0.67812	0.00449	0.36002	0.99621	23	80
Shan1	0.70016	0.00949	0.49123	0.90909	34	76

*Model based on Unrelated Question assuming $\pi_U = 1.0$

Table D.6: Tolerance Intervals for Different Methods with side = 2, $\alpha = 0.10$, $P = .90$

Method	$\hat{\pi}$	vâr	Lower π	Upper π	2-Sided Lower	2-Sided Upper
Warner	1.0000	0.01187	0.78649	1.0000	57	80
Singh-Joarder	0.78182	0.00448	0.65061	0.91303	45	77
Devore	0.71667	0.00596	0.56540	0.86793	38	74
Horvitz*	0.71667	0.00573	0.56826	0.86507	38	74
Soberanis-Cruz*	0.71667	0.00506	0.57724	0.85609	39	73
Mangat-Singh-Singh*	0.71667	0.00377	0.59639	0.83694	40	72
Frey	0.7875	—	0.5768	0.82909	39	72
ChangKuo1	0.6991	0.00363	0.58104	0.81717	39	71
ChangKuo2	0.67812	0.00449	0.54672	0.80952	36	70
ChangKuo3	0.70352	0.01232	0.48599	0.92104	32	77
Shan1	0.60983	0.00305	0.30269	0.91696	18	77
Shan3	0.67812	0.00449	0.33219	1.00000	20	80
Shan3	0.6939	0.00678	0.49135	0.89645	32	76

*Model based on Unrelated Question assuming $\pi_U = 1.0$

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